

TABLE 3—INCREMENT OF APPARENT MOMENT IN CARBON TETRACHLORIDE

Solute	μ_s (Benzene) (1)	μ_s (Carbon tetrachloride)	$\Delta\mu$ [[2] - (1)]
2-methyl quinoline	1.89	2.19	+0.30
6-methyl quinoline	2.25	2.30	+0.05
8-methyl quinoline	1.51	1.75	+0.24

The apparent inability of dielectric measurement in detecting a weak interaction corresponding to $\Delta\mu=0.05$ also assist in understanding the limitation of Earp and Glasstone theory.

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Synthesis of Phenacyl Dithiocarbamates and 2-Thio- Δ^4 -Thiazolines

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THIOCARBAMATES¹, dithiocarbamates²⁻⁶ and thiocarbamoyl aryldisulphides^{7,8} possess pesticidal characteristics. The preparation of phenacyl dithiocarbamates was, therefore, undertaken.

Ammonium, alkylammonium and dialkylammonium dithiocarbamates react with phenacyl bromide exothermically to give phenacyl dithiocarbamates, which, however, cyclize to 2-thio- Δ^4 -thiazolines, in the case of dithiocarbamates derived from primary amines. 2-Thio- Δ^4 -thiazolines⁹ too, are expected to be biologically active. Sahu *et al.*⁹ reported the synthesis of two such thiazolines. The infrared spectrum (KBr Pellet) of phenacyl dithiocarbamates shows carbonyl absorption around 1690 cm^{-1} , which is absent in that of 2-thio- Δ^4 -thiazolines.

Preparation of Phenacyl dithiocarbamates and 2-Thio- Δ^4 -Thiazolines :

Ethanolic solutions of a dithiocarbamate (0.02 mole, ammonium dithiocarbamate¹⁰ derived from an aromatic amine, alkylammonium/dialkylammonium dithiocarbamate derived from an aliphatic amine prepared by reacting the aliphatic amine with carbondisulphide in ethanolic solution) and phenacyl bromide (0.02 mole) are mixed and kept at room temperature for 4 hours. The product which crystallizes on chilling is collected by suction filtration and washed with water. Recrystallization from ethanol affords pure compounds. Melting points and yields are recorded in Table 1. All the compounds exhibited analytical data consistent with their molecular composition.

TABLE 1—PHENACYL DITHIOCARBAMATES AND 2-THIO- Δ^4 -THIAZOLINES DERIVED FROM VARIOUS AMINES

Amine	m.p. ¹ of dithiocarbamate/ thio-thiazoline	% Yield
1. Morpholine	134	85
2. Piperidine	120	85
3. Di-isopropyl	66	50
4. N-Methylaniline	154	70
5. Aniline ²	133	80
6. p-Chloroaniline ³	123	70
7. o-Toluidine	97	75
8. p-Toluidine	109-11	80
9. m-Toluidine	137	70
10. p-Anisidine	85	70
11. p-Phenetidine	198	70
12. n-Propyl	100	65
13. n-Butyl	80	60
14. mono Ethanol	85	50

(1) Melting points are uncorrected, compounds 1 to 4 are phenacyl dithiocarbamates and the rest are 2-thio- Δ^4 -thiazolines.

(2) Reported by B. Sahu, *et al.*

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Thin Layer Chromatographic Studies with Some Carbazoles : Hydrochloric Acid—A Convenient Spray Reagent for Carbazole Alkaloids

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CONCENTRATED hydrochloric acid has been found to be a good spray reagent for detection of carbazole alkaloids.

Thin layer chromatographic (tlc) methods have been found to be most suitable for detection and identification of minute amount of carbazoles from a given mixture¹. In each instance, the spots on the developed chromatograms were detected by means of their fluorescence under chromatolite or by the colour developed after spraying the chromatogram with picric acid. Later, we reported DDQ (2 : 3-dichloro-5, 6-dicyano benzoquinone) as a spray reagent with different carbazoles as substrates². The immediate blue to green coloration developed by spraying the spots proved to be convenient for detection of carbazoles. It was also proved to be more sensitive (0.1 μg) than picric acid (10.00 μg). However, DDQ is a quite toxic reagent.

In search for a better spray reagent for carbazole alkaloids, we noticed that non-phenolic carbazoles in contamination with phenolic ones give colour test (blue, violet, green spots) when sprayed with FeCl₃ solution. The characteristic colour reaction was also observed when sprayed with SbCl₅ solution.

The general behaviour could be explained by the fact that under experimental conditions metal chlorides could be considered to undergo hydrolysis as follows :

The resulting hydrochloric acids gave the colour reaction. Studies of the optical properties of the blue solid (also other coloured spots) in the visible

TABLE 1—COLOUR DEVELOPED AFTER SPRAYING THE CHROMATOGRAMS WITH CONC. HCl, WITH 5% FeCl₃ SOLUTION AND 10% SbCl₅ SOLUTION RESPECTIVELY

Compounds	Sources	Colour developed with			R _f
		Conc. HCl	5% FeCl ₃	10% SbCl ₅	
1. Carbazole	Fluka (Buchs, Switzerland)	Bluish violet	Bluish violet	Bluish violet	0.9
2. 3-methyl carbazole	<i>Clausena heptaphylla</i> Wt. and Arn.	Blue	Bluish green	Pinkish violet	0.8
3. Glycozoline	<i>Glycosmis pen'aphylla</i> Retz. D. C.	Blue	Blue	Blue	0.69
4. Glycozolidine	"	"	"	"	0.51
5. Murrayanine	<i>Murraya koenigii</i> Spreng.	Very faint blue on prolonged heating	Very faint blue on prolonged heating	Pale blue	0.35
6. Mukoic acid	"	Faint blue on heating	Faint blue on prolonged heating	"	0.25
7. Mukonine	"	"	"	"	0.36
8. Mukonidine	"	Blue on prolonged heating	Greenish blue	Blue	0.2
9. Girinimbine	"	Pink	Ash blue	Pinkish violet	0.76
10. Koenimbine	<i>Murraya koenigii</i> Spreng.	Pinkish violet	Ash blue	Pinkish violet	0.65
11. Heptazolidine	"	"	"	"	0.74
12. Koenidine	"	"	Greenish blue	"	0.25
13. Murrayacine	"	Blue on prolonged heating	Pale blue	—	0.35
14. Murrayazolidine	"	Bluish	Deep blue	Blue	0.39
15. Mahanimbine	"	Pink (dull)	Greenish blue	Bluish violet	0.93
16. N-Acetyl carbazole	Prepared in laboratory	No colour developed	No colour	No colour	—